

Unveiling Situation of Women Fornicator in the Society: A Revisitation of Nalini Jameela's "An Autobiography of a Sex Worker"

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Autobiography is a genre that gives the feelings of a writer. Women writers are taught to be obedient to write about her body, sexuality and her inner self is an achievement in itself. *THE AUTOBIOGRAPHY OF A SEX WORKER* (2007) written by Nalini Jameela is an outspoken and controversial autobiography that portrays how the female body uses as a weapon against the patriarchy on which the family's honor depends.

Unlike Kamala das, Jameela's autobiography creates a sharp considering controversial fact because of her lower-class Dalit background. If a Dalit woman happens to be a prostitute, then she is nonentity, who should make herself invisible because to acknowledge her presence would be a threat to the much - glorified ideals of modesty and virginity.

Virginity and modesty are two notions constructed by the patriarchal society to glorify women's body. We always talk about virginity and modesty only concerning woman and never with a man. This society wants a woman to be pure and respectable, one where man has no notions of being followed in their life. This patriarchal society expects woman shouldn't have any personal wishes rather they have to think of their family before they do anything to their own.

Through this autobiographical book, Nalini pointed out day to day struggle of women fornicator in the society. Here the researcher mentioned women sex workers as a fornicator. Fornicator means the love makers, the researcher pointed out that the sex workers are not only giving sexual pleasure to the customers, but they also taught them to use safety measures while doing sex.

Flavours of Literature

Sex workers also give them comfort and relaxation through talking which customers are lack at their home.

The greatest weakness of women is her own body. It is the site of violence against women. A Dalit woman who is untouchable by day becomes very much touchable by night. The priest cannot drink the water touched by her dirty hands, but he can have intercourse with her without regret. This reveal the hypocrisy of our Moral conscious society.

Women are always women; there is no difference in women who are bound in a family situation and who are doing sex work. The only difference is that the feminine who were behold in a family don't have right to decide when tobroke their virginity, it's in the hands of their husband, but these rules are not for sex workers. People consider the women who are doing sex work are a bad omento the society. The customers don't feel ashamed of going there, then why the sex workers alone have to feel inferior about their profession.

Sex work is also a profession like another profession. In this autobiography Nalini pointed out that when police came for, they used to leave the customers where they arrest sex workers. The customers have the rights to visit sex workers without regret, then why the workers have to feel inferior about doing their job in society. Women have all the right to take decisions in their life.

From an invisible sex worker, Nalini rose to become an activist. She made a daring statement in her autobiographical book that

There is no difference between a scientist who uses his rains, a teacher who uses his verbal abilities, a laborer who uses his hands, and a sex worker who uses her body.

Ethical motherhood and morality defined by patriarchy are identified as pillars to conserve female compel and they are depose and strip, exposing the stark reality of our hypocritical male dominant society.

To be pure and virgin was in the hands of a woman. If the woman lost their virginity before marriage, then the society calls that woman as the impure soul. But that rule was not implicated in the life of man. Man can have more than one wife, and they could do whatever they want in their life without restriction. These kinds of restrictions made women be the weaker sex in society when compared to men.

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